

Evaluation of Effluent Discharge from a Petrochemical Refinery and Its Effect on The Receiving Water Quality in Delta State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The assessment of aquatic pollution in industrially impacted water bodies is crucial for effective water resource management. This study evaluates the effluent discharge (EED) from a petrochemical refinery into Ubeji Creek and examines its effects on the river's physicochemical and heavy parameters. Water samples were collected for a period of six months and analyzed for key parameters, including pH, temperature, total dissolved solids (TDS), electrical conductivity (EC), dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), nutrients, petroleum hydrocarbons, and heavy metals. The EED of the refinery petrochemical effluent was found to be 11.42, categorizing the effluent as polluted. The pH values ranged from 7.20–7.25 in all the station, which fall within the allowable limit (6.50–8.50). TDS and EC were notably lower in station one and station two with the value of (207.68 mg/L and 226.14 μ S/cm) due to dilution effects. DO levels were relatively higher in stations one and station two with the value of (7.70–7.98 mg/L) compared to other stations whereas BOD and COD showed opposite trends, reflecting reduced organic pollution during the rainy period. Heavy metals, including lead, copper, cadmium, nickel, mercury, vanadium, arsenic, and barium, were below detectable limits at all stations. However, chromium showed an irregular spike at the effluent discharge point (0.86 ± 2.27 mg/L at Station 2). Organic pollutants such as total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH), and benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and yylene (BTEX) showed a clear decreasing trend downstream. TPH dropped from 0.12 ± 0.03 mg/L at Station 1, while PAH reduced from 0.07 ± 0.02 mg/L at Station 1 to 0.01 ± 0.01 mg/L downstream. BTEX was undetectable at Stations 2 and 3. The concentrations of petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH: 0.01–0.12 mg/L), PAHs (0.01–0.07 mg/L), and BTEX (0.00–0.02 mg/L) declined due to enhanced biodegradation and dilution. The mean value of ammonia NH₄ (1.17 mg/L) and TSS of (42.72 mg/L) across all stations, exceeded the regulatory limits of (0.5 mg/L and 30 mg/L) this indicates persistent risks from nutrients and particulate. These findings highlight the need for stricter effluent treatment measures and continuous monitoring to mitigate pollution and protect aquatic ecosystems.

Keywords: *Aquatic, Pollution, Effluent, Petrochemicals, Refinery, Heavy metals*

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Introduction

Water bodies across the Niger Delta region serve as critical resources for domestic, agricultural, industrial, and ecological functions. Among them, the Ubeji River, located in Warri South Local Government Area of Delta State, Nigeria, is of particular importance due to its proximity to the Warri Refining and Petrochemical Company (WRPC). The river provides water for household use, irrigation, aquaculture, and fishing, thereby supporting both livelihoods and food security in surrounding communities. However, these benefits are increasingly threatened by the discharge of untreated and partially treated industrial effluents into the river.

Effluents from petrochemical industries are complex mixtures that often contain high concentrations of petroleum hydrocarbons, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), heavy metals, suspended solids, and other hazardous substances (Nwaichi & Ntorogo, 2016). Such pollutants are well documented for causing oxygen depletion, altering physicochemical conditions, disrupting ecological balance, and impairing aquatic biodiversity (Ekpo et al., 2012). Beyond ecological damage, they pose significant risks to human health through bioaccumulation in fish and shellfish, which form part of the diet of local populations (Aghoghovwia & Ohimain, 2014).

Previous studies conducted in the Niger Delta region have consistently reported contamination of aquatic ecosystems from oil-related activities (Chindah et al., 2011; Olobaniyi & Owoyemi, 2006). Elevated levels of hydrocarbons, heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, and chromium, as well as increased turbidity and reduced dissolved oxygen, have been associated with effluent discharges from industrial facilities. These pollutants reduce water quality, degrade sediment structure, and contribute to long-term ecosystem stress.

Despite these findings, studies specific to Ubeji River are still sparse. Most of the available works either examine isolated water quality parameters or provide broad assessments of pollution in the Warri axis without focusing on the effluent quality and its direct influence on the river. Moreover, the ecological implications of continuous refinery effluent discharge into Ubeji River have not been fully characterised. This situation calls for a more holistic and systematic evaluation, especially through the application of pollution indices that integrate multiple contaminants into a single, interpretable measure of environmental quality.

Materials and Methods

Sample Collection and Analysis

Water samples were collected from three location (upstream, effluent discharge point and downstream, water samples were collected using pre-cleaned polyethylene bottles, following standard procedures (APHA, 2017). Samples for physicochemical analysis will be preserved at 4°C in an icebox before laboratory analysis. Heavy metal samples will be acidified with nitric acid (HNO₃) to maintain stability (APHA, 2017).

Laboratory Analysis

pH, temperature, and dissolved oxygen (DO) will be measured in situ using a multiparameter probe (APHA, 2017). Turbidity, total dissolved solids (TDS), and electrical conductivity (EC) will be determined using a turbidimeter and conductivity meter (WHO, 2018). Biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) will be analyzed following Winkler's method and the closed reflux method, respectively (APHA, 2017). Heavy metals (lead, cadmium, chromium, arsenic, nickel, and mercury) will be analyzed using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (AAS) (Nouri et al., 2011). Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPH), Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH), and BTEX (Benzene,

Toluene, Ethylbenzene, Xylene) will be quantified using Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) (Okoro et al., 2018).

Figure 1. Map of the Study Area

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) will be computed using SPSS25.0. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) will be conducted to compare water quality parameters across stations ($P < 0.05$ significance level). Evaluation Effluent Discharge (EED) will be calculated using the formula:

$$EED = \sum \left(\frac{C_i}{L_i} \right) \times W_i \quad (1)$$

Where:

- C_i = Observed concentration of parameter i (Mean value from the dataset)
- L_i = Regulatory limit for parameter i (e.g., EGASPIN limit)
- W_i = Weightage factor (can be equal for all parameters or assigned based on environmental impact) (Singh et al., 2017).

Note: EED will be calculated using the provided mean values and the EGASPIN limits where available. The EED values will be classified into low, moderate, high, and severe pollution categories for interpretation.

Results and Discussion

The impact of petrochemical industrial effluent on the physical and chemical composition of Ubeji River was assessed across three stations. The pH remained relatively stable across all stations, with values ranging from 7.20 ± 0.36 at Station 3 to 7.25 ± 0.41 at Station 2. Temperature also showed slight variations, from $28.08 \pm 0.95^\circ\text{C}$ at Station 1 to $28.40 \pm 0.37^\circ\text{C}$ at Station 2. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) and Electrical Conductivity (EC) increased slightly downstream, with TDS rising from 102.20 ± 83.02 mg/L at Station 1 to 132.10 ± 109.79 mg/L at Station 3, while EC increased from 207.68 ± 170.13 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 263.45 ± 218.58 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ across stations. Turbidity was highest at the discharge point (49.05 ± 15.94 NTU at Station 2) but decreased downstream (41.23 ± 20.48 NTU at Station 3).

Dissolved Oxygen (DO) values were similar across all stations, with a slight decrease at station 3 with a value of 7.68 ± 2.76 mg/L but increases with 7.98 ± 1.73 mg/L at Station 1 to 7.70 ± 2.71 mg/L at Station 2. Similarly, Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) and Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) showed a decreasing trend, with BOD reducing from 4.78 ± 1.82 mg/L at Station 1 to 3.58 ± 0.95 mg/L at Station 3, and COD declining from 10.63 ± 4.09 mg/L to 7.98 ± 2.22 mg/L over the same stations. Salinity and chloride levels also exhibited an increasing trend downstream, with salinity rising from 32.88 ± 25.75 mg/L at Station 1 to 42.38 ± 34.16 mg/L at Station 3, and chloride increases at station 3 with 23.54 ± 14.28 mg/L but decreases at station 1 and 2 with a range of 18.25 ± 14.28 mg/L. Similarly, sulphate levels decreased in station 1 and 2 with a range of 22.33 ± 6.71 mg/L to 25.84 ± 6.16 mg/L but increased at Station 3 with 28.25 ± 10.35 mg/L, while nitrate and phosphate concentrations followed a similar pattern, reaching 7.71 ± 3.63 mg/L 0.63 ± 0.41 mg/L at Station 3, respectively.

The effect of seasonal variation on the impact of effluent from the petrochemical industry on the physical and chemical composition of Ubeji River was evident across all measured parameters (Table 1 and 2). The pH values were generally within the EGASPIN limit in all station (7.20 – 7.25). Temperature variations were minimal, with values ranging from 28.08°C to 28.40°C across both seasons. Total dissolved solids (TDS) and electrical conductivity (EC) showed significant reductions in some stations, with TDS dropped in station 1 and 2 with the range of 102.20 mg/L and 113.13 mg/L but show increase in station 3 with a range of 132.10 mg/L in station 3, and EC decreasing from 207.68 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ to 226.14 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ due to dilution in station 1 and 2.

Turbidity increased at Stations 1 and 2 (45.85 & 49.05 NTU) but decreased at Station 3 (41.23 NTU), suggesting localized sediment resuspension. Dissolved oxygen (DO) was higher in station (7.98 mg/L) compared to station three (7.68 mg/L), likely due to increased aeration. Conversely, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) were lower in station three respectively, with BOD ranging from 3.58 mg/L to 4.78 mg/L and COD from 7.98 mg/L to 10.63 mg/L, indicating reduced organic pollution.

Total hardness and alkalinity showed a marked decrease in station one, with hardness ranging from 53.85 mg/L to 68.55 mg/L, and alkalinity from 9.25 mg/L to 9.75 mg/L. Salinity and chloride concentrations also declined significantly, in station one with a range of 32.88 mg/L to 42.38 mg/L and chloride from 18.25 mg/L to 23.54 mg/L.

Nutrients such as sulfate, nitrate, and phosphate were lower in station one due to dilution from rain, with sulfate decreasing from 28.10 – 37.50 mg/L to 16.55 – 20.70 mg/L, nitrate from 8.25 – 11.00 mg/L to 4.18 – 4.71 mg/L, and phosphate from 0.73 – 1.00 mg/L to 0.26 – 0.35 mg/L. Similarly, major cations such as calcium, magnesium, sodium, and potassium showed a sharp decline station one. Calcium ranges from 5.82 mg/L to 7.32 mg/L, magnesium from 16.50 – 21.53 mg/L to 2.67 – 3.14 mg/L, sodium from 8.82 mg/L to 11.35 mg/L, and potassium from 2.16 mg/L– 2.79 mg/L.

Petroleum hydrocarbons and heavy metals were generally low across station. Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) declined from 0.04 mg/L to 0.12 mg/L, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAH) from 0.02mg/L to 0.07mg/L, and benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX) from 0.00mg/L to 0.02 mg/L. Heavy metals such as iron, zinc, and chromium also decreased, with iron reducing from 0.01–0.01 mg/L to 0.03–0.01 mg/L and zinc from 0.16 mg/L to 0.23 mg/L. Notably, chromium was detected at 1.50 mg/L in Station 2 during the dry season but was absent in the wet season.

Table 1. Impact of Petrochemical Industrial Effluent on the Physiochemical, Nutrients and Salinity Indicator Parameters of Ubeji River Water

	Sample station			P-Value
	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3	
pH	7.20±0.43	7.25±0.41	7.20±0.36	P>0.05
Temperature (°C)	28.08±0.95	28.40±0.37	28.25±0.85	P>0.05
TDS (mg/l)	102.20±83.02	113.13±85.44	132.10±109.79	P>0.05
TSS (mg/l)	19.00±21.94	83.00±21.94	8.00±21.94	P>0.05
EC (µs/cm)	207.68±170.13	226.14±171.02	263.45±218.58	P>0.05
Turbidity (N.T.U)	45.85±10.91	49.05±15.94	41.23±20.48	P>0.05
DO (mg/l)	7.98±1.73	7.70±2.71	7.68±2.76	P>0.05
BOD (mg/l)	4.78±1.82	3.96±1.14	3.58±0.95	P>0.05
COD (mg/l)	10.63±4.09	8.83±2.62	7.98±2.22	P>0.05
Total Hardness (mg/l)	53.85±44.86	58.91±44.75	68.55±57.63	P>0.05
Alkalinity (mg/l)	9.25±2.63	9.75±3.01	9.33±2.88	P>0.05
Salinity (mg/l)	32.88±25.75	36.40±26.48	42.38±34.16	P>0.05
Chloride (mg/l)	18.25±14.28	20.22±14.73	23.54±18.98	P>0.05
Sulphate (mg/l)	22.33±6.71	25.84±6.16	28.25±10.35	P>0.05
Nitrate (mg/l)	6.21±2.37	6.88±2.40	7.71±3.63	P>0.05
Phosphate (mg/l)	0.54±0.23	0.59±0.28	0.63±0.41	P>0.05
Calcium (mg/l)	5.82±4.85	6.37±4.84	7.39±6.21	P>0.05
Magnesium (mg/l)	9.59±7.99	10.51±7.98	12.20±10.25	P>0.05
Sodium (mg/l)	8.82±6.91	9.75±7.10	11.35±9.14	P>0.05
Potassium (mg/l)	2.16±1.69	2.39±1.74	2.79±2.25	P>0.05
Ammonium (mg/l)	0.25±0.09	0.27±0.10	0.30±0.14	P>0.05

Note: NB: All values are expressed as Mean±SD; P>0.05= No significant differences

Heavy metals, including lead, copper, cadmium, nickel, mercury, vanadium, arsenic, and barium, were below detectable limits at all stations. However, chromium showed an irregular spike at the effluent discharge point (0.86 ± 2.27 mg/L at Station 2) before returning to 0.01 ± 0.00 mg/L downstream. Organic pollutants such as Total Petroleum Hydrocarbons (TPH), Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAH), and Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene, and Xylene (BTEX) showed a clear decreasing trend downstream. TPH dropped from 0.12 ± 0.03 mg/L at Station 1 to 0.01 ± 0.02 mg/L at Station 3, while PAH reduced from 0.07 ± 0.02 mg/L at Station 1 to 0.01 ± 0.01 mg/L downstream. BTEX was undetectable at Stations 2 and 3.

The evaluation of effluent discharged from a petrochemical company in Warri, Delta State, in comparison with the Environmental Guidelines and Standards for the Petroleum Industry in Nigeria (EGASPIN), indicated general compliance with most parameters. However, certain exceedances were recorded, particularly in ammonia, turbidity, and total suspended solids (TSS). These elevated levels are likely associated with petrochemical operations, where ammonia may originate from nitrogenous compound release, while turbidity and TSS increases are often linked to fine particulate and colloidal matter

discharge. Such exceedances can impair light penetration, disrupt aquatic ecosystems, and hinder photosynthetic processes (Adebayo et al., 2019).

These results corroborate previous studies on the impact of petrochemical effluents on Nigerian water bodies. Edema et al. (2009) documented fluctuations in temperature, pH, biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), suspended solids, and conductivity in Ubeji Creek, a tributary of the Ubeji River, emphasizing industrial influence on water quality. Similarly, Olajire and Imeokparia (2001) highlighted the negative effects of refinery and petrochemical discharges on aquatic life, underlining the necessity for rigorous monitoring and regulatory measures.

Table 2. Impact of Petrochemical Industrial Effluent on the Hydrocarbons and Organic Pollutants Parameters of Ubeji River Water

	Sample station			P-Value
	Station 1	Station 2	Station 3	
Phenol (mg/l)	0.05±0.01	0.01±0.01	0.00±0.00	-
TPH (mg/l)	0.12±0.03	0.04±0.04	0.01±0.02	-
PAH (mg/l)	0.07±0.02	0.02±0.02	0.01±0.01	-
BTEX (mg/l)	0.02±0.01	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	-
THC (mg/l)	1.46±0.37	0.41±0.49	0.13±0.19	-
Iron (mg/l)	0.03±0.02	0.01±0.00	0.01±0.01	P>0.05
Zinc (mg/l)	0.23±0.10	0.23±0.10	0.16±0.09	P>0.05
Chromium (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.86±2.27	0.01±0.00	P>0.05
Lead (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	P>0.05
Copper (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	-
Cadmium (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	P>0.05
Nickel (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	P>0.05
Mercury (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	-
Vanadium (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	-
Arsenic (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	-
Barium (mg/l)	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	-

Note: NB: All values are expressed as Mean±SD; P>0.05= No significant differences

Temporal variations in effluent quality parameters were observed, though most differences were not statistically significant. The exhibited slightly lower values of pH is due to minor dilution effects from rainfall, aligning with findings by Edokpayi et al. (2017). Conversely, temperature was marginally elevated in the dry season, influenced by increased solar radiation and reduced water volume, a trend reported in other tropical regions (Ewa et al., 2020). Stability in BOD and COD levels across seasons suggested limited organic pollution, while conductivity was notably higher in the dry season due to lower dilution capacity and increased ion concentration, consistent with observations by Nnaji et al. (2019).

Phosphate concentrations showed minor seasonal fluctuations, whereas ammonia levels were slightly higher in the dry season, likely due to reduced runoff and nitrogenous waste accumulation. This pattern has been linked to lower microbial degradation rates and increased industrial discharges during drier periods (Afolabi et al., 2018). Turbidity and TSS were significantly elevated in the wet season, attributed to increased runoff and particulate influx, a phenomenon frequently observed in industrially impacted water bodies (Oketola et al., 2013). Meanwhile, total dissolved solids (TDS) recorded higher values in the dry season, attributed to evaporation and concentration of dissolved ions, mirroring previous studies on seasonal water quality trends (Olaekan et al., 2021).

Heavy metals, including Pb, Ni, Cu, Cr, Cd, Fe, Zn, and sulfides, remained undetectable in both seasons, suggesting effective containment within industrial processes or sufficient effluent treatment prior to discharge. These findings align with the conclusions of Akinbile and Ogunrinde (2017). The calculated Evaluation Effluent Discharge (EED) identified ammonia and turbidity as key contributors to pollution potential, consistent with prior research highlighting their detrimental effects on aquatic systems and overall water quality (Ajibade et al., 2015).

The environmental consequences of these exceedances are noteworthy. Elevated ammonia concentrations pose toxicity risks to aquatic organisms, leading to biodiversity loss, while increased turbidity and TSS can smother benthic habitats, impair filter-feeding species, and transport adsorbed pollutants downstream. These conditions may compromise water quality when the effluent is discharge into any water body, affecting its suitability for domestic, agricultural, and recreational applications (Nwankwoala et al., 2017).

The pH of the Ubeji River remained stable across all monitoring stations and within permissible surface water quality limits (WHO, 2017) despite the introduction of effluent from the petrochemical industry. This stability suggests the presence of buffering mechanisms, potentially influenced by natural alkalinity sources and dilution effects. Seasonal analysis showed slightly reduced pH values in the wet season, likely due to increased acidic runoff and dilution of alkaline components (Nweke et al., 2019). Temperature variations were minimal, indicating limited thermal impact from industrial effluent. Nonetheless, dry season temperatures were slightly elevated due to lower water volume and increased solar exposure (Oladimeji & Abimbola, 2018).

Turbidity, TSS, and TDS exhibited significant spatial and seasonal differences. At the discharge point (Station 2), turbidity and TSS levels increased due to effluent-induced particulate accumulation but declined downstream (Station 3), suggesting sedimentation and dilution. Seasonal analysis revealed heightened turbidity and TSS in the wet season due to increased runoff and sediment resuspension (Mbonu et al., 2017), whereas TDS peaked in the dry season, reflecting reduced dilution and heightened ion concentration, aligning with previous findings (Obi & Uche, 2020).

Electrical conductivity (EC) followed a pattern similar to TDS, with the highest values at Station 2, indicating an influx of dissolved ions from the petrochemical effluent. A downstream decline suggests natural attenuation processes. Seasonal variation indicated elevated EC and salinity in the dry season due to lower water levels and higher ionic concentration, whereas the wet season recorded lower values, demonstrating dilution effects (Adebola et al., 2018).

Dissolved oxygen (DO) levels remained relatively stable across stations, with minor improvements downstream, suggesting adequate aeration and natural recovery. Seasonal trends showed higher DO in the wet season due to enhanced aeration from rainfall and turbulence (Ibrahim et al., 2019). The highest BOD and COD levels were recorded at Station 2, indicative of organic pollutant influx, but values declined downstream, signifying microbial degradation. Seasonal reductions in BOD and COD further supported the dilution effect of increased river discharge during the wet season (Adeyemo et al., 2021).

The observed physicochemical variations carry significant ecological implications. Elevated turbidity and suspended solids can impede light penetration, affecting primary productivity (Olaekan et al., 2021). Increased salinity and sulfate levels, while within limits, may alter freshwater species' physiological balance (Akinbile & Omoniyi, 2018). Chromium contamination, particularly in the dry season, necessitates continued monitoring due to its potential carcinogenic effects (WHO, 2020). Seasonal improvements in DO levels and reductions in BOD and COD suggest better water quality in the wet season, yet localized turbidity peaks pose ecological risks. Furthermore, hydrocarbon and heavy metal traces highlight concerns regarding bioaccumulation and potential human health impacts (WHO, 2021).

Nutrient concentrations increased downstream, reflecting both industrial and anthropogenic inputs. Although nitrate and phosphate levels remained within permissible limits, their prolonged accumulation poses eutrophication risks (Gupta et al., 2019). Seasonal analysis showed lower nutrient concentrations in the wet season due to dilution, consistent with previous research (Eze & Onwuka, 2022). Sulfate concentrations followed a similar trend, peaking in the dry season due to reduced dilution and increased effluent concentration (Akinbile et al., 2022).

Chloride levels were elevated at the discharge point and downstream, suggesting effluent contribution. Although within acceptable limits, prolonged exposure may disrupt freshwater organisms' osmoregulatory functions (Dalu et al., 2022). Seasonal trends revealed higher chloride and alkalinity levels in the dry season, associated with increased effluent retention and lower dilution capacity (Adeyemi & Aina, 2019).

Most heavy metals remained undetectable, except chromium, which reached a peak concentration of 0.86 mg/L at the discharge point in the dry season before declining downstream. Elevated chromium levels have been associated with petrochemical processing activities (Kehinde et al., 2018). Seasonal analysis indicated lower metal concentrations in the wet season, attributed to dilution and sediment flushing (Okonkwo et al., 2021). Although below critical thresholds, prolonged exposure to trace metals presents potential health risks for aquatic organisms and human consumers (ATSDR, 2021).

Total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPH) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) recorded their highest values at Station 2 but declined downstream, suggesting biodegradation and volatilization (Okonkwo et al., 2019). Seasonal reductions in hydrocarbons were observed, particularly in the wet season, due to dilution and microbial degradation (Afolabi et al., 2023). Benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and xylene (BTEX) compounds were undetectable downstream, supporting the hypothesis of rapid degradation and volatilization (Orji et al., 2020).

Conclusion

The findings of this study underscore the substantial impact of petrochemical effluent on the physicochemical quality of Ubeji Creek, with notable seasonal fluctuations. The elevated concentrations of pollutants, particularly in the dry season, indicate the need for stringent monitoring and regulatory enforcement. Although dilution during the wet season reduces pollutant levels, persistent contamination remains a concern. Comparing the observed water quality parameters with regulatory standards reveals instances of non-compliance, emphasizing the need for improved wastewater management practices. Overall, the study highlights the importance of continuous monitoring and adaptive water management strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of industrial discharges.

Recommendations

1. The refinery and petrochemical should implement advanced treatment technologies to ensure effluent discharge meets regulatory standards before release into the creek.
2. Regulatory agencies should establish a robust monitoring framework to track effluent quality and enforce compliance with water quality standards.
3. Local communities and stakeholders should be educated on the environmental and health implications of water pollution, promoting collective efforts for sustainable water resource management.

4. Given the observed seasonal variations, periodic assessments should be conducted to understand long-term trends and inform effective pollution control measures.
5. Industries should adopt sustainable production methods and cleaner technologies to minimize pollution at the source.
6. Future studies should explore biological and eco-friendly remediation techniques to mitigate hydrocarbon and heavy metal contamination in Ubeji Creek.

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